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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Abhaya D 9SU19NS001**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Abhirami Joseph 9SU19NS002**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Abhishek TN 9SU19NS003**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Abin Joseph 9SU19NS004**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Aksa M Jose 9SU19NS005**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Aleena A 9SU19NS006**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Anagha K Anil 9SU19NS007**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Anagha PJ 9SU19NS008**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Angel Maria 9SU19NS009**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AnjanaBiju 9SU19NS011**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Aparna VM 9SU19NS012**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Arya VK 9SU19NS013**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Ashly CS 9SU19NS014**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Aswin Nair 9SU19NS015**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BahamuniHansdak 9SU19NS017**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BibinBlesson 9SU19NS018**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Blesson S 9SU19NS019**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BlessyMol B.M 9SU19NS020**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CelinKuriakose 9SU19NS021**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Chakochoan James 9SU19NS022**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Christy Kuruvilla 9SU19NS023**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Gopika AV 9SU19NS024**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Greety Francis 9SU19NS025**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Hridya K.S 9SU19NS026**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IrfanFayis C.N 9SU19NS027**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Jismimol N Joseph 9SU19NS028**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JolsinaJoseph 9SU19NS029**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Jomol M 9SU19NS030**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Josini Joseph 9SU19NS031**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Josna Philip 9SU19NS032**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Karthika CR 9SU19NS033**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Kavya Suresh 9SU19NS034**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Liya V.C 9SU19NS035**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NafihaSulthana V 9SU19NS036**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Nandana K 9SU19NS037**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Nimisha Jenson 9SU19NS038**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PravithamolP 9SU19NS039**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RajinRajan M.V 9SU19NS040**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Rima John 9SU19NS041**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Rojan R 9SU19NS042**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sandra E 9SU19NS043**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sandra ElizebethRintu 9SU19NS044**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Shahana C.M 9SU19NS045**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SheethalDhanaraj K.T 9SU19NS046**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Shruthi.K.G 9SU19NS047**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sivapriya M 9SU19NS048**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sneha Jose 9SU19NS049**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sneha Judy T.J 9SU19NS050**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sona L.A 9SU19NS051**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SonaYesudas 9SU19NS052**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Swetha K.V 9SU19NS054**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Veena M 9SU19NS055**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding respectful maternity care among postnatal mothers”** in the 3rd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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